

PFAS-exposed zebrafish embryos show impaired innate immune response after infection with mycobacteria

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ABSTRACT

The *Per*- and polyfluoroalkyl substances PFNA, PFOA, PFOS and PFHxS have been regulated in the EU based on their interference with immune system functions. For many more environmental pollutants possible effects on immune function are unknown, so quick screening methods are required to determine which compounds are of highest immunotoxic concern. The aim of the present study was to optimize a test protocol to assess effects of chemicals on the innate immune system using zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) embryos. In a second step, the protocol was used to determine the immunotoxic effects of 11 PFAS on the innate immune response to pathogen infection. In the final protocol, zebrafish embryos were manually dechorionated 24 h after fertilization and subsequently infected with a transgenic strain of *Mycobacterium marinum* expressing the fluorescent protein mCherry. To avoid interference by systemic toxic effects that are not specific to the immune system, embryos were exposed to test compound concentrations that caused no developmental effects. Exposure was started immediately after infection. At 120 h after fertilization, the bacterial load, *i.e.* the integrated fluorescence intensity of bacteria in embryos exposed to the PFAS was compared to the integrated fluorescence intensity in infected vehicle-treated (control) embryos. In our optimized immunotoxicity assay, exposure to PFHxS and PFOA resulted in increased bacterial loads compared to vehicle treated embryos, indicating an increase in infection severity. Thus, the present study demonstrates that this zebrafish embryo immunotoxicity assay is useful to detect suppression of the innate immune system after chemical exposure.

1. Introduction

Immunotoxicology has been studied since the 1970s, when immunosuppressive properties were found for some environmental contaminants such as 2,3,7,8-tetrachlorodibenzo-p-dioxin (TCDD), organotin compounds and metals like lead, cadmium and arsenic (Vos, 2007). Exposure to compounds with immunosuppressive properties is associated with increased risk of infections and cancer in humans (Selgrade, 2007). Current European regulatory tests for chemicals regarding immunotoxicity include the histopathological assessment of the thymus, bone marrow and lymph nodes, and measurement of white blood cells in the 28-day repeated dose rat study (OECD, 2008). Furthermore, a developmental immunotoxicity cohort is included in the extended one-generation reproductive rodent toxicity study (OECD, 2018), in which the antibody response of the pups is assessed. While different

approaches to test immunotoxicity of fish are established (Rehberger et al., 2017), none of these methods were standardized and validated for the ecotoxicological risk assessment of immunotoxic effects of environmental chemicals.

Animal studies are expensive and time consuming and pose ethical problems due to animal suffering. Therefore, regulatory agencies aim to replace, reduce and refine (3R principle) the use of laboratory animals (Russell and Burch, 1959; Tralau et al., 2015). This also holds true for immunotoxicity testing. Currently *in vitro* data are only used to provide supportive evidence of specific mechanisms of toxicity (Germolec et al., 2017). For example, some studies have suggested that modulation of immune related genes mediates immunotoxicity caused by exposure to PFAS and TCDD (Hochstenbach et al., 2012; Pennings et al., 2016). However, the lack of standardized and validated test methods, makes the *in vitro* assays currently inappropriate as a basis for risk assessments

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(Segner et al., 2022).

Zebrafish embryos up to 5 days post fertilization have regularly been used to test for immunotoxicity (Rehberger et al., 2017; Trede et al., 2004; Zhao et al., 2024). As zebrafish embryos are not free-feeding at this early stage, they are considered non-protected life-stages according to European legislation (Strähle et al., 2012). The adaptive immune system of zebrafish only becomes functional 3 weeks after fertilization (Willett et al., 1999), while functional macrophages and neutrophilic granulocytes are already present within 3 days after fertilization (Lieschke et al., 2001). Zebrafish embryos are therefore useful to specifically determine effects on innate immunity (Habjan et al., 2024; Rehberger et al., 2017). Most of the studies on immunotoxicity with zebrafish embryos have focused on the molecular aspects of chemically induced immunosuppression, such as expression of immune related genes, the number of immune cells and the release of cytokines, without presence of pathogens (Zhao et al., 2024). However, only experiments with organisms infected with pathogens can provide relevant information on the ability of the innate immune system to fight off infections (Segner et al., 2022).

The infection of zebrafish embryos with fluorescent transgenic *Mycobacterium marinum* has often been used in the field of immunology and pharmacology to study basic mechanisms of infection in fish and screen compounds for their antibiotic effectiveness (Habjan et al., 2024; Habjan et al., 2021; Xie et al., 2021). At low infection concentrations, these bacteria do not interfere with the morphological development of the zebrafish embryos and can be visualized *in vivo* in the melanocyte deficient casper zebrafish strain (White et al., 2008). Furthermore, *M. marinum* infection is mostly controlled by macrophages in zebrafish embryos (Clay et al., 2007), which makes it suitable to determine effects on macrophage function, an essential part of the innate immune response to infections in all vertebrates.

Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are ubiquitous in the environment and have been found to interfere with multiple physiological processes, including liver function, endocrine function and immune function in humans (Fenton et al., 2021). The effects on the immune system were determined to be the most critical in the risk assessment of PFAS by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) (Schrenk et al., 2020). In this risk assessment a tolerable weekly intake of 4.4 ng/kg body weight of perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS), perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA), perfluorononanoic acid (PFNA) and perfluorohexanesulfonic acid (PFHxS) was derived (Schrenk et al., 2020). The first evidence for the immunotoxicity of PFAS came from epidemiological studies in which children from mothers with high concentrations of PFHxS, PFOA and PFOS in the blood serum were found to have lower antibody titers after vaccination compared to children from mothers with low concentrations of these PFAS in their serum (Grandjean et al., 2012; Granum et al., 2013). Despite these lower antibody titers, epidemiological studies have shown conflicting results regarding the association between exposure to PFAS and the incidence or hospitalization rates due to infectious diseases (Dalsager et al., 2021; Impinen et al., 2019; Okada et al., 2012; von Holst et al., 2021). Besides their impact on human health, a recent study (Birgersson et al., 2021) reported immunotoxic effects on feral fish from PFAS and PCB contaminated Swedish lakes, which underlines the need to investigate PFAS-induced immunotoxicity not only for human but also for environmental health.

Based on this background, the aims of the present study were to optimize a test protocol for the assessment of immunotoxicity in bacteria-infected zebrafish embryos and to use this protocol to determine the effects of exposure to 11 PFAS on innate immune function. The tested PFAS include the classic PFOA and PFOS, some alternatives with a shorter carbon chain, and GenX. These compounds are all persistent and are regularly detected in the aquatic environment (Evich et al., 2022).

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Zebrafish maintenance

Adult, melanocyte deficient casper zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) (White et al., 2008) were kept in recirculating tank systems at the Amsterdam Animal Research Center of the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam with a light/dark cycle of 14 h/10 h at 27 °C and pH 7.2. They were fed Skretting M-75 Gemma Micro dry food 2× per day, and living artemia 1× per day. A male:female ratio of 1:1 was used for breeding. Freshly fertilized eggs were collected in the morning and washed with egg water (60 µg/ml of “Instant Ocean” sea salt in demineralized water). The tank systems and fish at the Amsterdam Animal Research Center are checked annually for various diseases, including *Mycobacterium marinum*. The PCR test results for *M. marinum* are negative. Therefore, an endogenous infection of zebrafish embryos with *M. marinum* can be excluded.

2.2. Chemical solution preparation

Table 1 shows an overview of the selected PFAS tested in this study, together with their CAS number and supplier. All compounds had purities >95 %. Stock solutions of test compounds (100 mM) were made in 100 % DMSO (Thermo Scientific) for all PFAS, except for GenX, which was dissolved in 100 % methanol (Table 1). Dilutions of the stocks in 30; 10 and 3 mM were prepared in DMSO for PFOA, PFHxA, PFHxS and PFOS. A 10 mM stock solution of the immunosuppressant reference compound dexamethasone was prepared in DMSO.

The tested PFAS were also tested for their direct effects on growth of *M. marinum*. For this, a suspension of *M. marinum* (2×10^8 CFU/ml) was spread on an agar plate, and a droplet of 10 µl of each of the tested PFAS in the concentrations tested in the immunotoxicity experiments was added. The agar plate was placed upside down at 30 °C to prevent condensation from contaminating the agar surface, and the plate was visually inspected twice per day. No faster or slower growth of *M. marinum* was observed at the location of the droplets compared to the rest of the agar plate. Therefore, eventual effects of PFAS exposure on bacterial infection loads in zebrafish cannot be attributed to direct effects on *M. marinum* growth.

2.3. Developmental toxicity assay

To avoid interference with unspecific, systemic toxicity, the

Table 1
Tested compounds and their supplier.

Name	Abbreviation	CAS number	Supplier
Sodium trifluoromethanesulfonate	TFMSA	2926-30-9	Sigma-Aldrich
Perfluorobutane sulfonic acid	PFBS	375-73-5	Sigma-Aldrich
Perfluorohexane sulfonic acid	PFHxS	355-46-4	LGC standards
Perfluorooctane sulfonic acid	PFOS	1763-23-1	ABCR
Sodium trifluoroacetate	TFA	2923-18-4	Sigma-Aldrich
Perfluoropropionic Acid	PFPrA	422-64-0	Sigma-Aldrich
Perfluorobutanoic acid	PFBA	375-22-4	ABCR
Perfluorohexanoic acid	PFHxA	307-24-4	ABCR
Perfluorooctanoic acid	PFOA	335-67-1	Sigma-Aldrich
Hexafluoropropylene oxide dimer acid	GenX	13,252-13-6	ABCR
Sodium perfluoroethanesulfonic acid	PFETS	2837-92-5	Kanto Chemical
Dexamethasone	DEX	50-02-2	Sigma-Aldrich

immunotoxicity experiments were performed at exposure concentrations that did not cause developmental toxicity. Thus, test compounds were first screened for their effects on zebrafish embryo development and mortality. Exposure started either 2 or 24 h post fertilization (hpf) to determine the ideal time to start exposure in the immunotoxicity assays. All developmental toxicity assays were performed in three independent experiments ($N = 3$).

In short, zebrafish embryos were exposed to the test compounds either starting at 2 hpf or at 24 hpf, and developmental effects were assessed at 120 hpf. All embryos were manually dechorionated at 24 hpf. The embryos were assessed for the following developmental effects: lethality, developmental delay, edemas, craniofacial malformations and tail malformations.

In experiments starting exposure 2 hpf, healthy fertilized eggs were selected 2 hpf, and transferred to petri dishes (35 mm diameter) filled with 4 ml of egg water as a vehicle control, or 10 μM of DEX, which was chosen as the positive control for the immunotoxicity experiments, or one of the selected PFAS in an initial test concentration of 100 μM . If exposure to a PFAS at 100 μM resulted in developmental defects, it was tested again in 4 concentrations (3; 10; 30 and 100 μM) to determine the maximum tolerated concentration. Each exposure condition contained 0.1 % solvent (DMSO or methanol) and was tested in one petri dish containing 13 embryos. These petri dishes were incubated for 24 h at 28 °C. The 0.1 % solvent concentration was needed as some of the tested compounds were not soluble in DMSO in higher concentrations than 100 mM, which corresponds to 100 μM after 1000 \times dilution in egg water.

In the experiments starting exposure 24 hpf, healthy fertilized eggs were selected at 2 hpf and incubated at 28 °C in petri dishes (92 mm diameter) filled with 25 ml of pure egg water. Each petri dish contained approximately 100 eggs.

At 24 hpf, all embryos (*i.e.* those exposed 2 hpf and 24 hpf) were manually dechorionated and transferred to 6-wells plates with every well filled with 4 ml of egg water as a vehicle control, or 10 μM of DEX, or one of the selected PFAS in an initial test concentration of 100 μM . When exposure to a PFAS at 100 μM resulted in developmental defects, it was tested again in 4 concentrations (3; 10; 30 and 100 μM). Each exposure condition contained 0.1 % solvent (DMSO or methanol) and was tested in one well containing 13 embryos. The plates were incubated at 28 °C for 4 more days.

The embryos were assessed for developmental defects and lethality at 5 days post fertilization. The percentage of embryos that showed any developmental defect (lethality, developmental delay, edemas, craniofacial malformations and/or tail malformations) was calculated separately in each of three independent experiments. Then the average over the three percentages was calculated and bar charts with error bars representing the standard deviation were made in Graphpad Prism V10.2.3 (Graphpad Software, La Jolla, CA, USA). Exposure concentrations that induced developmental defects or mortality in less than 10 % of the embryos were further tested in the immunotoxicity assays. The 10 % cutoff value was chosen based on the OECD test guideline for the fish embryo acute toxicity test (OECD, 2013). In the OECD test guideline, an increase in lethality larger than 10 % compared to the vehicle-treated embryos leads to the compound being further tested to characterize the hazards. We avoided testing concentrations that induce unspecific developmental effects as we were interested in detecting specific effects on the immune system.

2.4. Immunotoxicity assays

Transgenic *M. marinum* M^{USA} bacteria expressing the fluorescent protein mCherry in a pSMT3 vector (van der Woude et al., 2014) were cultured in flasks at 30 °C in Middlebrook 7H9 medium (Difco-BD Biosciences) supplemented with 10 % ADC (albumin, dextrose and catalase) and 0.02 % tyloxapol to prevent clotting. When the bacteria suspension showed the characteristic orange color of *M. marinum*, the suspension

was centrifuged, supernatant medium was discarded, and the bacteria were resuspended in PBS supplemented with 20 % glycerol and 0.02 % tyloxapol. This procedure was repeated two times, after which the bacteria were diluted to an optical density (OD) of 4, which corresponds to 400 colony forming units (CFU) per nanoliter (Benard et al., 2012). This suspension was aliquoted in 50 μl volumes in Eppendorf tubes and stored at -80 °C.

Healthy fertilized casper zebrafish eggs were selected at 2 hpf and incubated in petri dishes (92 mm diameter) filled with pure egg water at 28 °C for 24 h. The embryos were manually dechorionated at 24 hpf, and incubated in pure egg water for 2 more hours at 28 °C before starting the infections. Embryos were anesthetized in 0.02 % MS-222 and placed in an agarose (1.5 % in MilliQ water) grid to be infected with fluorescent *M. marinum* by injection in the caudal vein. The injections were performed following the protocol by Benard et al. (2012), their article also includes a video of the caudal vein injections. The embryos were individually injected by microinjection with 1 nl of a 1:1 dilution (V:V) of the *M. marinum* stock suspension in a phenol red solution (0.5 % in PBS). Each embryo was thus injected with around 200 CFU of fluorescent *M. marinum*.

After injection, the number of CFUs injected into the embryos was determined by plating 1 nl of the bacterial suspension on a Middlebrook 7H10 agar plate. After 1–2 weeks of incubation at 30 °C, the number of colony forming units on the plate was counted to confirm that around 200 CFUs were injected in each embryo.

After injection, the embryos were transferred to 6-wells plates, 15 embryos per well, with each well containing either 4 ml of egg water with 0.1 % DMSO or methanol (vehicle control) or 4 ml of egg water containing one of the PFAS in a concentration that induced <10 % teratogenic effects (final solvent concentration 0.1 % DMSO or methanol). Egg water with 10 μM DEX was used as a positive control for immunosuppression. To keep the number of embryos to inject manageable, the PFAS were split in two groups. As the vehicle control and reference compound DEX were tested in both groups, they were tested in six independent experiments. Each test compound was tested in 30 embryos ($n = 2$ wells) in each of three independent experiments ($N = 3$), except for TFMSA and PFPrA ($N = 2$).

In each experiment, one well contained 15 dechorionated embryos that were not injected, but also exposed to 0.1 % DMSO or methanol, to determine the background fluorescence without infection with fluorescent *M. marinum*. The plates were incubated at 28 °C. At 5 dpf, embryos were anesthetized again in 0.02 % MS-222 and fluorescence micrographs were taken using an Olympus IX83 microscope and a Hamamatsu ORCA-Flash 4.0 camera and CellSens software (4 \times magnification, excitation/emission wavelengths: 550/610 nm). Bright-field micrographs were also taken to determine the shape of the embryo and accurately select it to calculate the integrated fluorescence intensity. The integrated fluorescence intensity per embryo was calculated with CellProfiler 4.2.6 (Broad Institute, Cambridge, MA, USA). Within each experiment, the average integrated fluorescence intensity of the embryos exposed to 0.1 % solvent was calculated. The integrated fluorescence intensities of all the embryos within the experiment were divided by this average to obtain the fold change compared to the average of the vehicle controls. The fold changes were ²log transformed and plotted in a scatterplot in Graphpad Prism.

All statistics on the data were performed in Graphpad Prism. The untransformed data as well as ²log transformed and square root transformed data were not normally distributed according to the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (Lilliefors, 1967). Therefore, a two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed on ranked fold changes (Akritas, 1990), with experiment number and treatment as independent variables. As the two-way ANOVA did not indicate statistically significant differences between replicate experiments, fold changes per compound were combined from all experiments and further analyzed by one-way ANOVA on ranked fold changes, with treatment as the only independent variable. Differences between treatments were considered

significant if the adjusted p after Dunn's test was <0.05.

3. Results

3.1. Developmental toxicity assay

Exposure to PFOA, PFHxA, PFHxS and PFOS induced developmental toxicity at exposure concentrations of 100 μM or lower (Fig. 1). The developmental toxicity of PFOA, PFHxA, PFHxS and PFOS decreased when the start of the exposure was delayed from 2 hpf to 24 hpf. When exposure was started at 2 hpf, the concentration that caused developmental effects at 120 hpf in <10 % of the embryos was 3 μM for PFOA, PFHxA and PFHxS, while all tested concentrations of PFOS induced developmental effects in >10 % of the embryos. When exposure was started at 24 hpf, the concentration that caused developmental effects at 120 hpf in <10 % of the embryos was 30 μM for PFOA, PFHxA and PFHxS, and 3 μM for PFOS. To allow exposure to higher concentrations of the PFAS, and thereby having a higher probability of detecting their potential immunotoxic effects, exposure in the immunotoxicity assays was decided to start at 24 hpf.

Fig. 1. Percentage of embryos with one or more (sub)lethal developmental defects (lethality, developmental delay, edemas, craniofacial malformations and/or tail malformations) after exposure to 0; 3; 10; 30 and 100 μM of test compounds. The developmental effects were assessed at 120 hpf. The bars show the average percentage over the three independent experiments, and the error bars show the standard deviations. (A) effects after exposure starting at 2 hpf. (B) effects after exposure starting at 24 hpf. All embryos in both experimental setups were manually dechorionated at 24 hpf. PFAS that induced no developmental effects at 100 μM are not shown.

3.2. Immunotoxicity assay

In each experiment, the number of CFUs of *M. marinum* injected in each embryo was also spread on a Middlebrook 7H10 agar plate. The number of CFUs on the agar plates varied between 172 and 304.

A statistically significantly higher fold change in fluorescence (integrated density, corresponding to bacterial load) was observed in the dexamethasone exposed embryos compared to vehicle exposed embryos (Fig. 2). The median $^2\log$ fold change of the vehicle exposed embryos was -0.12 , with the interquartile range: -0.97 - 0.36 , whereas the median $^2\log$ fold change in embryos exposed to 10 μM dexamethasone was 0.72 , with interquartile range: -0.06 - 1.47 . Exposure to 30 μM PFOA and 30 μM PFHxS also resulted in statistically significantly higher bacterial loads compared to vehicle exposed embryos. The median $^2\log$ fold change in embryos exposed to PFOA was 0.42 , with interquartile range: -0.42 - 1.02 . The median $^2\log$ fold change in embryos exposed to PFHxS was 0.70 with interquartile range: 0.13 - 1.27 . None of the other tested PFAS showed statistically significant changes in bacterial load at the highest concentration not causing developmental effects, i.e. 100 μM , except for PFOS (3 μM). The background fluorescence of the yolk in non-infected embryos was negligible (data not shown in Fig. 2). Representative micrographs of zebrafish embryos exposed to vehicle control, DEX, PFOA, PFHxS) and embryos that were not injected with fluorescent bacteria are shown in Fig. 3.

4. Discussion

The aim of the present study was to optimize an existing test protocol with zebrafish embryos to allow the assessment of decreased immune response in embryos exposed to xenobiotic test compounds. The original protocol has been used in immunology and drug-development, mostly to assess decreased bacterial load after exposure to candidate antibiotic drugs (Habjan et al., 2021). In a second step, we used the resulting protocol to determine the effects of exposure to PFAS on innate immune function after bacterial infection.

The use of zebrafish embryos as a model organism to test for effects

Fig. 2. Scatter plot showing the $^2\log$ (fold change in integrated fluorescence intensity) of each embryo measured at 5 dpf. The lines indicate the median in each exposure group. As the embryos were infected and exposed at 24 hpf to their respective compound, each embryo was exposed and infected for a total of 4 days. Only exposure to reference compound dexamethasone (10 μM), and test compounds PFOA and PFHxS (30 μM) resulted in a statistically significant increase in bacterial load. The other PFAS were all tested at 100 μM , except PFOS which was tested at 3 μM . The plot of vehicle control (VC) and DEX include 180 data points from 6 different experiments, the plot of PFPPrA and TFMSA include 60 data points from 2 different experiments, the plot of all other PFAS include 90 data points from 3 different experiments. *: p -value <0.05.

Fig. 3. Micrographs of 5 dpf zebrafish embryos showing an overlay of the fluorescence micrographs (excitation/emission: 550/610 nm) with the bright-field micrographs. Orange spots indicate the bacterial infection with *M. marinum*. Representative zebrafish embryos from the three independent repeats of the experiment. A) Infected embryos exposed to the vehicle (0.1 % DMSO). B) Infected embryos exposed to the positive control dexamethasone (10 μ M). C) Infected embryos exposed to PFOA (30 μ M). D) Infected embryos exposed to PFHxS (30 μ M). E) Embryos that were not infected with bacteria. Scale bar = 500 μ m.

on the wildlife vertebrate and human innate immune system is supported by the largely conserved immune system of vertebrates (Stein et al., 2007). As the lymphoid cells of the adaptive immune system only mature after approximately three weeks in zebrafish (Willett et al., 1999), only specific effects on the innate immune system can be assessed in zebrafish embryos less than 5 days old. This is also the age limit at which the use of zebrafish embryos is not restricted by European legislation on animal welfare (Strähle et al., 2012). Two days after fertilization, zebrafish embryos already develop macrophages morphologically similar to those in mammals, which are able to phagocytose bacteria (Herbomel et al., 1999). Zebrafish embryos have also been found to express homologs of most human Toll-like receptors (TLR), the NF- κ B transcription factor and homologs of the most important cytokines (Sullivan and Kim, 2008). Therefore, effects on the immune function in zebrafish embryos can be extrapolated to effects on the innate immune system in humans and other vertebrates.

The zebrafish embryo model has been used in the field of immunotoxicology, mostly to determine effects on the molecular or cellular level (Rehberger et al., 2017; Zhao et al., 2024). Commonly measured parameters include phagocytic activity, expression of genes related to the immune system, and respiratory burst activity (Rehberger et al., 2017). These parameters can give valuable insight into specific mechanisms of

immunotoxicity, but they don't show whether or not this mechanism leads to adverse effects, for example faster progression of infections. As decreased resistance to pathogenic bacteria is an adverse effect, we developed our test protocol using zebrafish embryos infected with *M. marinum*. This *M. marinum* infection model has been used extensively in research on the pathophysiology of tuberculosis (Habjan et al., 2024; Myllymäki et al., 2016), but also on effects of corticosteroids on the immune system (Xie et al., 2021). As *M. marinum* infections are mostly controlled by macrophages, increases in bacterial load are indicative of decreased macrophage functioning (Clay et al., 2007).

During the development of the test protocol, many small adjustments were made to lead to the optimized protocol presented in this study. Manual and automated injection of *M. marinum* in the yolk of freshly fertilized zebrafish eggs were tried out, but mortality rates were too high. Therefore, we continued with caudal vein injection of 1-day old embryos, which required dechoriation of the embryos to reach the vein. This increased the workload, but decreased the mortality rates. Injection of lower concentrations of bacteria (50 and 100 CFU/embryo) was tested, but resulted in even larger variation in fluorescence at 120 hpf, so we decided to use 200 CFU/embryo. Finally, we chose to expose the zebrafish embryos to the test compounds at 24 hpf as earlier exposure resulted in teratogenic effects at very low concentrations of PFOS, PFOA, PFHxA and PFHxS (Fig. 1). As zebrafish embryos develop mature neutrophils and macrophages around two days after fertilization, this exposure window was still useful to examine effects on the innate immune system.

Finally, a suitable immunosuppressant positive control had to be identified. Using a similar setup with zebrafish embryos infected with *M. marinum*, a previous study (Xie et al., 2021) reported decreased phagocytic function of macrophages after exposure to the glucocorticoid beclomethasone. Exposure to beclomethasone resulted in an average 2.3-fold increased bacterial load, compared to vehicle treated embryos. Another common reference compound is the glucocorticoid DEX (Giles et al., 2018). In our immunotoxicity assay, we obtained a mean of 2.27 and median of 1.65-fold increase after exposure to our reference compound, the glucocorticoid DEX, compared to vehicle treated embryos. Consequently, it was selected as positive control.

When using the final test protocol with our selected PFAS, we also observed increased bacterial loads after exposure to PFOA and PFHxS, but no statistically significant change in bacterial load after exposure to the other seven tested PFAS. Therefore it seems that the PFAS with a longer carbon chain, except PFOS, induced effects on the immune system. The lack of effects by PFOS in the present study might be explained by the test concentration that was 10-fold lower than that of PFOA and PFHxS, as higher concentrations of PFOS induced developmental effects. A limitation of the method we used is that organisms in early embryonic stages are relatively sensitive to systemic toxicity (Mohammed, 2013). In assays using organisms in later life stages, higher concentrations could probably be tested due to lower sensitivity to systemic toxicity. This would make it possible to test PFOS at higher concentrations, and thereby more reliably assess its potential immunotoxicity. However, the use of adult fish is contrary to the 3R principle and the embryos have the advantage that they are more susceptible to infections than adult fish (Lieschke et al., 2001).

The larger immunotoxic potential of long-chain PFAS compared to short-chain PFAS is in line with an earlier study by Tang et al. (2023), in which PFBA and PFOA were tested in zebrafish embryos infected with *Vibrio parahaemolyticus*. That study has some similarity with ours, as they also infected the zebrafish embryo with a pathogenic bacteria. However, *V. parahaemolyticus* is far more virulent in fish (Zhang et al., 2016) than *M. marinum* (Prouty et al., 2003). This explains the difference in readout between their study (Tang et al., 2023) and ours, as they measured infection induced lethality and we measured integrated fluorescence intensity as a proxy for bacterial load. In addition to effects on infection induced lethality, Tang et al. (2023) reported a correlation between longer PFAS carbon chain and increased numbers of circulating

neutrophils and activation of the TLR pathway (Tang et al., 2023). Remarkably, all effects reported by Tang et al. (2023) occurred at test concentrations almost three orders of magnitude lower than ours. We currently have no explanation for this difference.

Earlier studies with zebrafish embryos have also shown that exposure to PFOA leads to decreased migration of neutrophils after an inflicted tail injury (Pecquet et al., 2020). This effect was attributed to decreased chemotaxis of the leukocytes (Pecquet et al., 2020). As chemotaxis plays an important role in the innate immune response (Schluger and Rom, 1997), this might explain the effects of PFOA in our assay. The immunotoxic potential of PFOA is further illustrated by studies in adult mice in which exposure to PFOA impacted the phagocytic activity of white blood cells (Guo et al., 2021; Vetvicka and Vetvickova, 2013).

PFAS have also been found to cause immunotoxicity in other rodent studies (Ehrlich et al., 2023; Phelpis et al., 2024). These studies show that many PFAS, including PFOS, PFOA, PFHxA and PFBS, can cause decreased lymphoid organ weights, altered lymphocyte subpopulations and histopathological changes in bone marrow in rodents (Ehrlich et al., 2023). Histological changes in bone marrow could explain the decreased functionality of the innate immune system found in the present study, as it could lead to decreased numbers or decreased maturity of monocytes/macrophages and neutrophils. Additionally, a host infection study in mice showed that exposure to PFOS resulted in a decreased clearance of *Citrobacter rodentium* (Suo et al., 2017). However, the mice from that study were adults with a functional adaptive immune system which makes it difficult to compare with our results in zebrafish embryos.

In summary, however, there is clear evidence from multiple vertebrate studies and epidemiological studies in humans, that PFAS have a high immunotoxic potential. This is also illustrated by the use of immunotoxicity as the most critical endpoint in the risk assessment of PFAS by EFSA (Schrenk et al., 2020). Two of the PFAS on which the risk assessment by EFSA was based, PFOA and PFHxS, also showed activity in the present study. As macrophages play a critical protective role during *M. marinum* infection (Clay et al., 2007), we hypothesize that the effects we report could be due to effects on macrophages. Macrophages are not only phagocytes, but also act as antigen presenting cells and can thereby play a role in the activation of B cells and subsequent antibody production. Therefore, the effects we observed could possibly be related to the decreased antibody production after vaccination in children exposed to PFOA and PFHxS (Grandjean et al., 2012; Granum et al., 2013). Assessment of mechanistic, molecular endpoints would be required to confirm this hypothesis.

A limitation of the immunotoxicity assay we developed is the overall high degree of biological variation and small effect size in all exposure groups, even the positive control DEX, with a median fold change of 1.65 compared to vehicle treated controls. The large biological variation within groups is also found in negative controls zebrafish embryos injected with *M. marinum* in studies focusing on antibiotic drug development (Habjan et al., 2021). Still, this assay was sensitive enough to detect the expected immunotoxicity of PFHxS and PFOA at the tested concentrations.

We used 100 μM as the exposure concentration for compounds that induced no developmental effects. This is six orders of magnitude higher than the concentrations that are regularly detected in European surface waters (Podder et al., 2021). We decided not to test compounds at concentrations higher than 100 μM to avoid problems of solubility, and to keep the solvent concentration at 0.1 %. On the other hand, we tested higher concentrations than found in the environment because the aim of the study was to determine the intrinsic immunotoxic properties of PFAS. Furthermore, our exposure duration of four days is very short compared to the long-term exposure in humans and wildlife animals due to the notorious persistence and bioaccumulation of these PFAS (Espartero et al., 2022). It can be assumed that a bacterial infection in an immuno-suppressed zebrafish embryo will become more severe with longer incubation time that exceeds the 5-day limit, which we wanted to

respect in our study considering the 3R principle. Therefore, we suggest using this assay as a prioritization tool to screen compounds for their immunosuppressive activity in only one high concentration that is below systemic toxicity. Positive compounds can then be further investigated, for example in epidemiological studies for human risk assessment, or in adult fish for environmental risk assessment. Positive compounds could also be further investigated using zebrafish embryos or *in vitro* assays, for example to assess phagocytic activity, expression of genes related to the immune system, immune cell migration, or respiratory burst activity (Corsini and Roggen, 2017; Rehberger et al., 2017).

Next to providing an optimized immunotoxicity screening test, the present study adds to the evidence that exposure to some PFAS has adverse effects on the immune system. Our results show that exposure to PFHxS and PFOA leads to a less efficient clearance of bacterial infection by the innate immune system. The present study has a focus on PFAS, but there are many other groups of compounds which can affect the immune system, like endocrine disrupting chemicals or specific pesticides (Corsini et al., 2013; Sabuz Vidal et al., 2021), that should be tested in the future. Our protocol provides a comparably easy test method that is in compliance with the 3R principles to assess effects of compounds on the innate immune function relevant for human and environmental health.

Research data

All raw data obtained in the present study is included in the supplementary materials. Supplementary material 1 contains the raw data from the developmental toxicity assays. Supplementary material 2 contains the raw data from the immunotoxicity assays.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Maxim P. Carlier: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Theo Verboom:** Visualization, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation. **Laura Cuijpers:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Lisa Baumann:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology. **Wilbert Bitter:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Software, Resources. **Timo Hamers:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.taap.2025.117484>.

Data availability

The data is available in the supplementary materials of this article

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